

Feature Selection Fusion Based Person Verification by Finger-Writing of a Simple Symbol

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Abstract: Writer verification is a form of biometrics. Among its various approaches, finger-writing verification of a simple symbol is aimed at being the most convenient, in which a user is verified by writing a simple symbol with a finger on a smartphone screen. In a previous study, an error rate of approximately 10 % was achieved. Furthermore, by selecting and fusing individually high-performing features, an equivalent error rate was obtained, even though the number of features used was reduced. In another previous study, we selected features that were resistant to tracing. In this study, we propose new feature selection methods focusing on individuality and independence, and a fusion method that combines them with two conventional selection methods. By using the proposed method, we finally achieved the error rate of approximately 6-7 %.

Keywords: Biometrics, Writer Verification, Finger-writing, Simple Symbol, Feature Selection Fusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

The total number of mobile subscriptions worldwide is expected to reach approximately 8.83 billion in 2025, with smartphone subscriptions expected to reach 7.41 billion [1]. As the means of connecting to the Internet has shifted from personal computers to smartphones, anyone can now easily access a wide variety of services, including online banking, social networking, and online shopping. While the world has become more convenient, the increase in cybercrime has become a serious problem. This has led to a growing need for more secure personal authentication, and biometric authentication in particular has been attracting attention in recent years [2].

Biometrics can be broadly divided into methods based on body parts (physical characteristics) and methods based on human habits (behavioral characteristics). We focus on writer verification, which belongs to the behavioral characteristics category. Writer verification is a method of verifying individuals based on their writing habits. Currently, signature verification is the most common form of writer verification [3]. However, signing is time-consuming, and writing a signature on a smartphone's small screen is difficult and inconvenient. To solve this problem, we proposed a method based on finger-writing of a simple symbol, in which users write a simple symbol with their finger on a smartphone screen [4]. Furthermore, we confirmed that the verification performance was equivalent to that when all features

were used, even though we selected and fused highly discriminative features to reduce the dimensionality [5]. We also proposed a feature selection method that was robust against tracing attacks [6]. In the proposed verification method, because everyone writes the same symbol, it is easy to imitate the original handwriting, so using features that are resistant to this is effective.

In this study, we propose a method for selecting features with higher individuality. Individuality is evaluated from the ratio of inter-individual variance to intra-individual variance. Furthermore, we also introduce principal component analysis (PCA) as a method for selecting independent features. We then propose a verification method that combines these two feature selection methods with two conventional feature selection methods.

II. VERIFICATION BASED ON FINGER-WRITING OF A SIMPLE SYMBOL

Signature verification is the most common form of writer verification, but it is difficult to sign on a small screen such as that of a smartphone, and the need for a dedicated pen makes it inconvenient. Therefore, we proposed writer verification based on finger-writing of a simple symbol [4]. In this paper, we refer to this as PV-FSS. In this method, the user writes a simple, globally known symbol directly on the smartphone screen with a finger for verification. Thus, no dedicated pen is required, and there is no need to memorize complex writing

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content. In addition, since the writing time is about one second, the method offers extremely high convenience.

A. Previous studies

For verifying individuals, 55 features listed in Table 1 were used [4]. These were fused (concatenated) to a multidimensional feature at the feature level and verification was performed using Euclidean distance matching and a support vector machine (SVM), which is a representative supervised machine learning method.

Verification is to determine whether a person who claims to be a legitimate user is actually the user. This determination is made by comparing the biometric features of a legitimate user pre-registered in the authentication system with those of the claimant. For this reason, the process is divided into an enrollment phase and a verification phase as shown in Fig. 1.

In the enrollment phase, with the Euclidean distance matching, a template is created by averaging multiple pieces of feature data, for example. With SVM, a model that distinguishes between one user and other users is trained using the feature data of the one user and the other users, and this is done for all users. One SVM model is specialized and prepared for each user.

In the verification phase, with the Euclidean distance matching, the distance between the claimant's biometric features and the template is calculated, and if the result is below a threshold, the claimant is determined to be the legitimate user; otherwise, the claimant is determined to be not the legitimate user (impostor). In SVM, the claimant's biometric features are input to an SVM model of a legitimate user specified by the claimant and evaluated. Each model is trained to assign +1 to a user and -1 to others, and if the output exceeds a threshold, the claimant is determined to be the user. If the output

Fig. 1 Enrollment and verification in Euclidian distance matching and SVM.

Table 1 Extracted Features in PV-FSS [4].

No.	Feature
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1	Maximum X coordinate
2	Y coordinate at maximum X
3	Maximum Y coordinate
4	X coordinate at maximum Y
5	Minimum X coordinate
6	Y coordinate at minimum X
7	Minimum Y coordinate
8	X coordinate at minimum Y
9	Average X coordinate
10	Average Y coordinate
11	Difference between the maximum and minimum X coordinates (Difference X)
12	Difference between the maximum and minimum Y coordinates (Difference Y)
13	Distance between start and end points
14	Drawing area size
15	Writing time
16	Maximum finger pressure
17	X coordinate at maximum pressure
18	Y coordinate at maximum pressure
19	Minimum finger pressure
20	X coordinate at minimum pressure
21	Y coordinate at minimum pressure
22	Average finger pressure
23	Maximum contact area
24	X coordinate at maximum contact area
25	Y coordinate at maximum contact area
26	Minimum contact area
27	X coordinate at minimum contact area
28	Y coordinate at minimum contact area
29	Average contact area
30	Maximum acceleration
31	X coordinate at maximum acceleration
32	Y coordinate at maximum acceleration
33	Minimum acceleration
34	X coordinate at minimum acceleration
35	Y coordinate at minimum acceleration
36	Average acceleration
37	Maximum velocity
38	X coordinate at maximum velocity
39	Y coordinate at maximum velocity
40	Minimum velocity
41	X coordinate at minimum velocity
42	Y coordinate at minimum velocity
43	Average velocity
44	Start point X coordinate
45	Start point Y coordinate
46	Start point finger pressure
47	Start point contact area
48	Acceleration around start point
49	Velocity around start point
50	End point X coordinate
51	End point Y coordinate
52	End point finger pressure
53	End point contact area
54	Acceleration around end point
55	Velocity around end point

does not exceed the threshold, the claimant is determined to be an impostor. Setting this threshold too high makes it easier to reject genuine users, reducing the user-friendliness of the authentication system. On the other hand, setting it too low makes it easier to mistakenly accept non-users as users, reducing the security of the system. The threshold is set based on a trade-off between usability and security.

The verification results are shown in Table 2, where experimental subjects wrote a circle, triangle, or square. The equal error rate (EER) was used to evaluate verification performance. The false rejection rate (FRR) is the rate at which genuine users are incorrectly rejected as impostors, while the false acceptance rate (FAR) is the rate at which impostors are incorrectly accepted as genuine users. When the threshold for determining whether a user is genuine is varied, FRR and FAR exhibit a trade-off relationship, and the point at which these two error rates are equal is called the EER. A smaller EER indicates better verification performance. A kernel function (linear, polynomial, or RBF) and two parameters (c and γ) for SVM were selected to minimize the EER from all combinations.

Table 2 EER [%] of PV-FSS Using Euclidean Distance Matching and SVM [5].

	Circle	Triangle	Square
Euclid	9.9	12.1	11.9
SVM	22.4	23.1	21.3

As a similar biometric verification operating on smartphones, a method based on flick gestures has been proposed [7]. In this method, features were extracted from finger flick gestures in the directions displayed on the smartphone screen, and verification was performed using Euclidean or Manhattan distance. The dataset consisted of 16 flicks per subject (four in each direction), collected 11 times from 10 participants, and eight features used are the starting coordinates (x, y), trajectory length, curvature, velocity, angle, pressure, and contact area. As a result, an EER of 1.5 % was achieved, which is a higher verification performance compared to the results shown in Table 2. However, performing 16 flicks requires considerable effort and time. In contrast, PV-FSS requires writing only one symbol for verification, making the required time short. Since convenience is an important factor in verification on a smartphone, which is used many times a day, PV-FSS has an advantage in terms of usability.

B. Feature Selection

In general, SVM based on machine learning can achieve higher verification performance than simple Euclidean distance matching; however, as shown in Table 2, contrary to expectations, the use of Euclidean distance matching resulted in better performance for all symbols. One possible reason for this is overfitting caused by the excessive number of feature dimensions. As the dimensionality of training data increases, the amount of data required to build

a highly accurate model grows exponentially [8]. As a result, the training dataset prepared in [4] was insufficient for adequate learning, leading to inappropriate classification of verification data and a decline in overall performance.

Therefore, it is important to reduce the dimension while selecting features that include individual differences. Furthermore, by selecting features from multiple perspectives and integrating them, it is expected that a more advanced verification system can be realized. While selecting highly discriminative features is effective in improving verification performance, it is desirable to select independent features to increase fault tolerance. Feature selection is not limited to a single perspective.

B-1. High Verification Performance Features

In [5], features that individually showed high verification performance were selected and fused at the feature level to evaluate the verification performance. Hereafter, the features selected by this method are referred to as “high verification performance features.” Table 3 shows the top 10 high verification performance features and their EER when writing a circle, triangle or square symbol.

Table 3 Top 10 High Verification Performance Features and Their EER [%].

	Circle	Triangle		Square	
Diff. Y	24.2	Max. finger pr.	22.9	Max. finger pr.	21.5
Drawing a. size	24.2	Max. contact a.	23.6	Av. contact a.	22.1
Max. contact a.	24.4	Av. contact a.	25.0	Max. contact a.	22.3
Av. vel.	24.7	Drawing a. size	26.8	Av. finger pr.	25.8
Writing time	24.7	Av. vel.	27.4	Drawing a. size	26.3
Av. contact a.	25.1	Writing time	27.7	End point finger pr.	26.3
Diff. X	25.6	Av. finger pr.	28.8	End point contact a.	26.8
Av. finger pr.	26.3	Diff. Y	29.4	End point X coord.	27.3
Min. Y coord.	27.6	Diff. X	30.4	Av. vel.	27.4
Av. acc.	27.6	End point contact a.	30.8	Diff. Y	27.9

Furthermore, Table 4 shows the verification results using Euclidean distance matching after fusing the top 10 features at the feature level. Although fewer features were used comparing with when all features shown in Table 2 were fused,

almost the same verification performance was obtained. This suggests that features with low discrimination performance do not contribute much to verification based on Euclidean distance.

Table 4 EER [%] by Feature Level Fusion of the Top 10 High Verification Performance Features.

Circle	Triangle	Square
10.2	11.0	10.3

B-2. Tracing-Resistant Features

Since PV-FSS uses handwriting, it is more resistant to theft and forgery than biometrics based on physical characteristics such as face or fingerprints. However, this does not mean that it is completely free of vulnerabilities. Potential vulnerabilities include the ease of duplication and the difficulty of concealment. Writing on a smartphone screen is easily visible to others. Since all users write the same simple symbol, it is also easy to imitate. For this reason, in [6], experimental participants practiced imitating others' handwriting in advance, and when actually imitating, they traced the handwriting while watching the writing. The verification performance of the handwritten data under such conditions was then evaluated, and we found features that provided high verification even when tracing handwriting, i.e., tracing-resistant features.

Fig. 2 shows a schematic representation of the data variability of a feature. The top image shows a user's (normal) handwriting, while the bottom image shows the traced version. (a) shows the case where the variability of the traced data is greater than that of the normal data, while (b) shows the opposite. When the variability of the traced data is greater than

Fig. 2 Diagram showing variabilities in feature data [6].

that of the normal handwriting, as in (a), it indicates that tracing is not successful, and such features are considered robust and resistant to tracing.

Therefore, using the subject's own handwritten data and the tracing data, we calculated the ratio of the variance of traced data to the variance of normal data, averaged it across all subjects, and examined the features for which this ratio exceeded 1 for all symbols. From the results, we excluded features that were considered to be affected by the experimental environment or the equipment used, and selected the 10 features shown in Table 5 as being resistant to tracing. Conversely, features that were commonly included in the bottom 10 for all symbols were selected as being non-resistant to tracing. These are shown in Table 6.

Table 5 Tracing-resistant features [6].

Minimum contact area
Maximum contact area
Average contact area
Start point contact area
End point contact area
Minimum finger pressure
Maximum finger pressure
Average finger pressure
Start point finger pressure
End point finger pressure

Table 6 Non-resistant features to tracing [6].

Difference X
Difference Y
Drawing area size

III. NEW FEATURE SELECTION

Considering various feature selection methods is similar to methods for aggregating opinions during discussions. Selecting features with high individual verification performance is like gathering talented people and listening to their opinions, increasing the reliability of the results. Gathering people with a variety of opinions increases robustness: even if one person makes a mistake, others can correct it. Just as there is no single way to gather people's opinions, there is also no single method for feature selection.

A. High-Individuality Feature Selection

In this study, we consider the strength of individuality as a new perspective for feature selection. Features with high individuality are defined as features with small intra-individual variability and large inter-individual variability. Specifically, we calculate the ratio of inter-

individual variability to intra-individual variability for each feature, and features with a large ratio are called “high individuality features.” Hereinafter, this ratio will be simply referred to as the “variance ratio.”

A-1. Variance Ratio

Let us explain how to calculate the variance ratio. If there are N pieces of data per subject, each of which is x_n ($n = 1$ to N) and their average is \bar{x}_k , then the intra-individual variance is defined as follows:

$$V_k = \frac{1}{N} [(x_1 - \bar{x}_k)^2 + (x_2 - \bar{x}_k)^2 + \dots + (x_N - \bar{x}_k)^2] \quad (1)$$

If the number of subjects is M , the mean intra-individual variance for all subjects is:

$$V_{tra} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M V_k \quad (2)$$

Next, let $\bar{\bar{x}}$ be the average of \bar{x}_k across all subjects, the mean inter-individual variance is defined as:

$$V_{ter} = \frac{1}{M} [(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{\bar{x}})^2 + (\bar{x}_2 - \bar{\bar{x}})^2 + \dots + (\bar{x}_M - \bar{\bar{x}})^2] \quad (3)$$

Finally, the variance ratio F is obtained as follows:

$$F = \frac{V_{ter}}{V_{tra}} \quad (4)$$

A-2. Results

Table 7 lists, in descending order of variance ratio, the top 10 features for each symbol along with their values. As can be seen, features such as writing time, velocity/acceleration, finger pressure, and finger contact area features, that cannot be visually confirmed during writing, ranked high. It is thought that individual differences were unconsciously exhibited during writing, and those were stable within individuals, resulting in large variance ratios.

Furthermore, while coordinate features did not rank high, difference between the maximum and minimum X coordinates, and the difference between the maximum and minimum Y coordinates did, likely because coordinate differences are relative values, unlike absolute values such as the maximum or minimum coordinate. The reason why end point velocity and acceleration had larger variance ratios than those at the starting point is that some subjects firmly stop their finger at the end, while others finish with a flicking motion. This makes individuality more apparent at the end of writing than at the beginning, resulting in larger variance ratios.

Table 7 Top 10 features with the highest variance ratio and their values for each symbol.

	Circle		Triangle		Square
Writing time	9.3	Max. contact a.	7.8	Start point Y coord.	12.4
Acc. around end point	8.7	Writing time	7.6	End point Y coord.	10.7
Start point Y coord.	8.6	Max. finger pr.	7.4	Writing time	9.0
Vel. around end point	8.6	Drawing a. size	7.1	Max. contact a.	7.9
Av. vel.	7.6	Vel. around end point	6.5	Max. finger pr.	7.4
Drawing a. size	7.6	Acc. around end point	6.5	Drawing a. size	7.2
End point Y coord.	7.5	Av. contact a.	6.0	Diff. Y	6.7
Diff. Y	6.6	Start point Y coord.	5.8	Min. Y coord.	6.4
Diff. X	6.6	Ave. vel.	5.7	Av. contact a.	6.0
Y coord. at min. acc.	6.5	Min. Y coord.	5.5	Av. vel.	5.8

A-3. Evaluation of Verification Performance

Table 8 shows the verification performance when the top 10 features with the highest variance ratios were fused at the feature level and verification was performed using Euclidean distance matching. For comparison, the results when the bottom 10 features with the lowest variance ratios were fused are also shown. Fusing the top 10 features improved verification performance for triangle and square symbols compared to using all features. In contrast, when the bottom 10 features were fused, the verification performance worsened. These results indicate that the proposed feature selection based on variance ratio makes it possible to quantitatively identify features that are both stable within individuals and discriminative across individuals, thereby enabling the selection of effective features for verification. By eliminating features that did not contribute to verification, the overall accuracy improved, demonstrating the effectiveness of this feature selection method.

Table 8 EER [%] when fusing the top 10 and the bottom 10 features with variance ratios.

	Circle	Triangle	Square
Top 10	13.1	10.8	8.4
Bottom 10	37.2	36.2	38.1

B. Independent Feature Selection

Our previous study [9] confirmed that fusing uncorrelated features improves verification performance. In that study, we selected a feature and

examined its correlation with other features in advance and fused highly correlated features. However, selecting only highly correlated features from a large number of features is difficult; it is not easy to simultaneously evaluate the correlation between three or more features. In this study, we achieve uncorrelated feature fusion by applying PCA to the multidimensional feature after feature-level fusion. However, when performing the PCA, data standardization is required. This can be achieved through normalization. In [9], it was found that the min-max method is particularly effective; therefore, we adopt it in this study. After the normalization, the mean value is subtracted from each data point to set the mean to zero. This is defined as standardization.

Additionally, dimensionality reduction is possible when using PCA. When converting features into uncorrelated, independent features, the number of dimensions can be reduced to a number that preserves the characteristics in the original multidimensional space. By reducing the dimension while maintaining the verification performance, the number of features that the SVM learns can be reduced, resulting in shorter learning time.

IV. FEATURE SELECTION FUSION

Table 9 shows the verification performance by each feature selection method. Specifically, the top 10 features were fused for the high verification performance and the high individuality feature selection methods, while the ten features discussed in Table 5 were fused for the tracing-resistant feature selection. SVM was used for verification.

Table 9 EER [%] for each feature selection method.

	Circle	Triangle	Square
High verification performance feature	8.4	8.2	7.7
High individuality feature	11.3	7.6	7.5
Tracing-resistance feature	15.8	17.4	15.3

In all selection methods, verification performance improved compared to the case of fusion of all 55 features using SVM, as shown in Table 2.

A. Fusion Method

Just as it is better to aggregate opinions from various perspectives, fusing various feature selection methods may result in better verification performance. Figure 3 shows the processing flow of

Fig. 3 Processing flow of the proposed verification method based on four feature selection fusion.

the proposed verification method based on feature selection fusion. First, 30 features, including 10 high verification performance features, 10 tracing-resistant features, and 10 high individuality features, are fused into a 30-dimensional feature. Features selected by three methods are shown in Tables 10-12. At this stage, the same features may be selected by multiple methods, resulting in feature duplication during feature fusion. Therefore, we propose two methods: one that fuses 30 features even if overlapping occurs, and another that treats overlapping features as a single feature. The former represents the case where overlaps are allowed, and the latter represents the case where overlaps are not allowed. In the latter case, the number of features is reduced to less than 30. Next, PCA is applied to the multidimensional feature generated to reduce and de-correlate its dimensions, achieving the fourth feature selection method described in III-B. Finally, the PCA scores are used for training or verification by SVM.

Table 10 Selected features (Circle).

High verification performance	Tracing-resistant	High individuality
Difference Y	Minimum contact area	Writing time
Drawing area size	Maximum contact area	Acceleration around end point
Maximum contact area	Average contact area	Start point Y coordinate
Average velocity	Start point contact area	Velocity around end point
Writing time	End point contact area	Average velocity
Average contact area	Minimum finger pressure	Drawing area size
Difference X	Maximum finger pressure	End point Y coordinate
Maximum finger pressure	Average finger pressure	Difference Y
Minimum Y coordinate	Start point finger pressure	Difference X
Average acceleration	End point finger pressure	Y coordinate at min. acceleration

Table 11 Selected features (Triangle).

High verification performance	Tracing-resistant	High individuality
Maximum finger pressure	Minimum contact area	Maximum contact area
Maximum contact area	Maximum contact area	Writing time
Average contact area	Average contact area	Maximum finger pressure
Drawing area size	Start point contact area	Drawing area size
Average velocity	End point contact area	Velocity around end point
Writing time	Minimum finger pressure	Acceleration around End point
Average finger pressure	Maximum finger pressure	Average contact area
Difference Y	Average finger pressure	Start point Y coordinate
Difference X	Start point finger pressure	Average velocity
End point contact area	End point finger pressure	Minimum Y coordinate

Table 12 Selected features (Square).

High verification performance	Tracing-resistant	High individuality
Maximum finger pressure	Minimum contact area	Start point Y coordinate
Average contact area	Maximum contact area	End point Y coordinate
Maximum contact area	Average contact area	Writing time
Average finger pressure	Start point contact area	Maximum contact area
Drawing area size	End point contact area	Maximum finger pressure
End point finger pressure	Minimum finger pressure	Drawing area size
End point contact area	Maximum finger pressure	Difference Y
End point Y coordinate	Average finger pressure	Minimum Y coordinate
Average velocity	Start point finger pressure	Average contact area
Difference Y	End point finger pressure	Average velocity

B. Performance Evaluation

To evaluate the verification performance of the proposed system, we used the dataset used in [4]. In this dataset, 30 subjects wrote three symbols (circle, triangle, and square) 20 times each. Of the 20 writing samples, 10 were used to train SVM models, and the remaining 10 were used for verification (test). The SVM was constructed as a one-versus-all model for each user (subject). Each model was trained using 10 data sets from one subject and 10 data sets randomly selected from each of the remaining 29 subjects. Similarly, 10 data sets from each subject and 10

randomly selected data sets from each of the other 29 subjects were used in verification.

Here, the selection of 10 data sets from the 29 subjects was random, so the data used during training and the data used for verification were not the same. Therefore, the verification performance in this study includes evaluation of subject data that was not trained. In real applications, there are cases where a third party attempts to impersonate a registered user, and coincidentally, the verification performance results in this study include such third-party spoofing. However, the frequency with which third-party spoofing occurs is not constant due to the random data selection mentioned above. In extreme cases, the subjects randomly selected from the 29 people for training and verification may be the same, in which case the results do not assume third-party spoofing. Conversely, if the subjects in training and verification are completely different, the verification performance results only assume third-party spoofing. Please note that the assumptions regarding third-party spoofing in this study are not strict.

To eliminate dependence on specific combinations of training data and verification data, cross-validation was performed 10 times. 10 out of 20 data sets for each subject were randomly selected for training, and the rest were used for verification. The data selection from 29 other subjects was as described above. By repeating this 10 times, we reduced dependence on data selection. The EER shown below is the average value from 10 cross-validations.

Table 13 shows the results of verification using the proposed feature selection fusion. These results outperformed the verification performance obtained using all features, as shown in Table 2. Furthermore, compared to the verification performance using 10 features selected from each of the three feature-selection perspectives shown in Table 9, the proposed method demonstrated better verification performance for all symbols.

Table 13 EER [%] by the proposed feature-selection fusion in overlapping allowed and not allowed cases.

Overlapping	Circle	Triangle	Square
Allowed	6.4	7.4	6.9
Not allowed	6.4	7.9	7.0

When overlapping was not allowed, the EER was slightly larger than when overlapping was allowed, meaning that verification performance was slightly degraded. By not allowing overlapping and treating

overlapping features as a single feature, the number of features was reduced to 20 for circle, 17 for triangle, and 18 for square. The slight deterioration in verification performance when overlapping was not allowed is thought to be due to the reduced number of features. On the other hand, the fact that nearly equivalent verification performance was achieved even with a reduced number of features is thought to be due to the effect of the proposed feature selection fusion method.

Figure 4 shows EER when varying the number of dimensions for each symbol, where the overlapping was allowed. The case of 30 dimensions was when no dimensionality reduction is performed. Even with a certain degree of dimensionality reduction, the EER did not change much, and when the dimensions were reduced to 5 dimensions, the number of feature dimensions is too small, so the EER increased and verification performance decreased. However, when the number of dimensions were reduced to 10, verification performance did not deteriorate. The equivalent verification performance could be obtained even when the number of dimensions was reduced to one-third. Reducing the number of dimensions shortens the processing time, enabling more efficient processing. For example, the processing time for 5 dimensions was reduced by about 10 % compared to 30 dimensions. Since there are some processes that do not depend on the number of dimensions, the processing time is not reduced to one-sixth.

Note that the dataset used for evaluation in this study did not involve tracing and therefore robustness to tracing was not evaluated. However, features that are resistant to tracing, i.e., features that do not lose their individuality even when traced, are thought to exhibit high individuality even when not traced, contributing to improved verification performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

As feature selection methods for PV-FSS, we have proposed methods for selecting features that individually show high verification performance and features that are resistant to tracing. In this study, we first proposed a method for selecting features that show high individuality as a new perspective for feature selection. Furthermore, we proposed verification by fusing four feature selection methods, including a method for selecting independent features. Specifically, we selected 10 features each

Fig. 4 EER [%] when varying the number of dimensions for each symbol.

from features with high verification performance, features with tracing-resistance, and features with high individuality, and created a single multidimensional feature by fusing them at the feature level. This was converted into a multidimensional feature with independent dimensions using PCA, while simultaneously reducing the number of dimensions, and training and verification were performed using SVM. The effectiveness of the proposed method was confirmed by comparing it with a conventional method that uses all features and a conventional method that uses features selected by each selection method. It is very interesting that verification performance with an error rate of 6-7 % was achieved across 30 subjects simply by writing a simple symbol on a smartphone screen with one's finger.

However, we need to aim for an error rate of 0 %, and further improvements are needed in the future. We plan to investigate the optimal number of dimensions for each feature selection in order to further improve verification performance. The introduction of stronger verification methods is also an issue to be considered. Deep learning technology can be used for verification, but the current dataset is insufficient to fully realize the potential of deep learning. Therefore, this study employed SVM, which demonstrates high verification performance even with small datasets. In order to introduce deep learning and improve the reliability of the results obtained this time, it is important and essential to expand the dataset.

Furthermore, when considering application to smartphones, data on the smartphone owner can be obtained by registering the data when starting use, but data on anyone other than the owner cannot be obtained. In this case, it is necessary to prepare data on other people in the system beforehand, or use a

classifier that can learn using only the owner's own data, such as a one-class SVM.

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